

Evaluating Yield Performance of White Yam (*Descorea Rotundata*) Variety to Different Planting Techniques for Enhancing Production

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ABSTRACT: This study was carried out in Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku, Rivers State to evaluate the yield performance of white yam variety to different planting techniques. The design adopted for the study was Complete Randomized Block Design (CRBD) with three treatments, each replicate five (5) times and in five (5) experimental blocks. The treatments were three (3) planting methods including: flat/hole, heap/mound and sack-bag techniques. The cultivation was completed during the first planting season of the year. Weeding, staking and other cultural practices were duly observed. Measurements were taken on tuber length, tuber girth/size, number of tubers per planting technique and the tuber fresh weight. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics tool and the Duncan multiple range scale for mean separation. The result showed that heap/mound planting technique consistently outperformed flat/hole and bag method in tuber length (37.80cm) and tuber size/gilt (27.60cm), number of tubers (32) and tuber fresh weigh (113.16 t/ha), indicating its superiority for vigorous tuber development. Also, test of significance on the tuber performance of white yam (*Descorea rotundata*) variety across different planting techniques for enhancing production showed that differences in the means of tuber lengths, number of tubers and tuber fresh weight of the different planting techniques were statistically significant at the 5% alpha level in favour of heap/mound planting technique. It was concluded that farmers should adopt all the three methods of yam planting depending on resource availability, land conditions, and management objectives, but where vigorous and appreciable tuber development is desired heap/mound planting is strongly recommended.

KEYWORDS: Evaluating, Yield Performance, White Yam Variety, Planting Techniques, Enhancing Production

INTRODUCTION

Yam (*Dioscorea* spp.) is a major staple crop in West Africa, Asia, and parts of the Caribbean, providing food security and income for millions of smallholder farmers (Odinwa et al., 2019). Unlike cereals, yam is vegetatively propagated, meaning that planting materials are derived from tubers or vegetative plant parts rather than seeds. According to Asiedu and Sartie (2017), the choice of planting material and planting method significantly influences yam establishment, growth, yield, and disease transmission. However, traditional planting systems are often constrained by low multiplication rates, high cost of seed yam, and the spread of pests and diseases, necessitating the development of improved planting techniques.

Yam is one of the most culturally, economically, and nutritionally important root and tuber crops in humid or tropical regions, mostly in West Africa, which produces over 90% of the world's yams (FAO, 2023). In countries such as Nigeria, Ghana, Benin, and Côte d'Ivoire, yam cultivation is not only an agricultural practice but also a cultural institution, entrenched in festivals, rituals, and land inheritance systems. Despite the availability of improved agronomic technologies, traditional planting methods continue to dominate yam production systems, particularly among smallholder farmers who account for more than 80% of total yam output (Ennin et al., 2022).

Traditional methods of yam planting are characterized by manual land preparation, minimal mechanization, and reliance on indigenous ecological knowledge, such as flat or hole, mound/heap/ridge and recently by yam bag technique. These methods have developed in response to local soil types, rainfall patterns, and labor availability, making them highly adaptive but also labor-intensive and vulnerable to yield decline under population pressure and climate changeability (Asiedu & Sartie, 2017).

The flat or hole planting technique is one of the simplest traditional methods of yam planting, practiced mainly in regions where soil conditions are naturally suitable for tuber development without extensive land shaping. Unlike mound/heap or ridge planting, this method does not involve the construction of raised soil structures. Instead, farmers plant yam setts directly into shallow holes dug on flat land. This system is commonly used in riverine areas, floodplains, sandy or loamy soils, and regions with low soil compaction, where natural soil structure provides adequate drainage and aeration (Aighewi et al., 2021). Flat planting eliminates the need for mound or ridge construction, reducing labor input by up to 50–60% compared to mound planting. This makes it attractive to farmers with limited labor or financial resources (Ennin et al., 2022). It is particularly prevalent in areas with seasonal

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flooding, where planting begins after water recedes and the soil remains loose and moist; and it is highly site-specific and cannot be widely applied across diverse agro-ecological zones, limiting its adoption in many yam-growing regions (Asiedu & Sartie, 2017). The mound/heap planting method is the oldest and most widely practiced traditional method of yam cultivation in West Africa and other tropical regions where yam (*Dioscorea* spp.) is a staple food crop. This method has been practiced for centuries and is deeply entrenched in the cultural identity of yam-producing communities, particularly in Nigeria, Ghana, Benin, and Côte d'Ivoire. Historically, the size and number of yam mounds constructed by a farmer symbolized wealth, agricultural expertise, and household food security. In many communities, mound preparation marks the beginning of the farming season and is often associated with communal labor and cultural rituals (Asiedu & Sartie, 2017). It involves the manual construction of raised soil heaps (mounds) using hoes or other hand tools. These mounds are typically conical or dome-shaped, measuring 0.5–1.0 m in height and 1.0–1.5 m in diameter, depending on soil type, rainfall, and yam variety. Each mound receives one yam sett or whole tuber, which is planted at the top or slightly below the crest of the mound at a depth of approximately 10–15 cm. After planting, the mound is often covered with organic mulch, such as dry grasses, leaves, or crop residues, to conserve soil moisture, suppress weeds, and regulate soil temperature. As the vines emerge, staking is introduced to support climbing growth and enhance photosynthesis.

Mound spacing is usually wide (1–1.5 m apart) to allow sufficient space for vine spread and to facilitate field operations (Aigheui et al., 2021). Mounds improve soil porosity, allowing better oxygen diffusion to the roots and tubers. This reduces anaerobic conditions and minimizes the incidence of rot-causing pathogens, especially in regions with prolonged rainfall (Ennin et al., 2022). The ridge planting system is a modified traditional yam planting method that developed in response to increasing population pressure, labor scarcity, and the need for higher land use efficiency in yam-producing regions of West Africa. Unlike the mound system, which relies on isolated soil heaps, ridge planting involves forming long, continuous raised soil ridges across the field, on which yam setts are planted at regular intervals. This system retains many benefits of traditional mound planting while allowing higher plant density and easier field management (Ennin et al., 2022). Ridge planting is increasingly promoted by agricultural extension services because it serves as a transition system between purely traditional and semi-mechanized yam production, making it suitable for smallholder farmers seeking to increase productivity without completely abandoning indigenous practices (Asiedu & Sartie, 2017).

Yam-bag technique is a recent innovation employed to raise yam at any available surface on land whether the land is fertile or not, whether it is smooth or rocky, plain or sloppy. It is the use of different types of waste bags (sack, cement, jute etc.) that can house required soil for the growth of yams throughout the growing season. With this technique, yams can be planted by the wall or fence within the yard whether cemented or interlocked. Growing yams in bags can serve as ornamental plants for ecstatic view or decoration during the vegetative growth and as food and source of income at maturity. This practice of planting yams in wasted bags around homes will put away fear of theft of yam products from the farm by thieves, an act that have stopped many farmers from cultivating yams in distant farms. It will reinvigorate mass participation in yam gardening that has gone moribund for decades in some parts of Rivers State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In as much as white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) has remained a staple crop in many tropical regions, its yields are often below potential because farmers use diverse planting techniques with little empirical guidance. Although methods such as flat/hole, heap/mound and sack/bag are commonly practiced, there is insufficient comparative information on how these techniques affect the yield of different yam varieties. This lack of evidence prevents recommendation of the most productive, cost-effective planting technique for improving tuber yield and supporting food security and farm incomes. The study therefore seeks to determine how flat/hole, heap/mound and sack/bag planting techniques influence the yield and yield components of a white yam variety (*Dioscorea* spp.) in particular, and to identify the most appropriate practice under local agronomic and socio-economic conditions.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the yield performance of white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) variety to different planting techniques for enhancing production. Specific objectives include to comparing:

- i. the tuber length (cm) of white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) variety across the three planting techniques.
- ii. the tuber girth (cm) of white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) variety across the three planting techniques.
- iii. the number of tubers per planting method of white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) variety across the three planting techniques.
- iv. the tuber fresh weight (t/ha) of white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) variety across the three planting techniques.

A hypothesis was stated to further shape the study.

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H₀₁: Yield performance of white-yam (*Descorea rotundata*) variety planted using different methods does not differ significantly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (ONELGA), Rivers State. It was an experimental field study; the design adopted was CRBD with three treatments each replicated five (5) times and in five (5) experimental blocks. The treatments were three (3) planting methods including: flat/hole, heap/mound and sack/bag. The trial site was cleared, stumped and marked out. Seedbeds were constructed randomly on the plots according to predetermined parameters in each replicate at a planting distance of 1m by 1m, a foot path of 0.6m by 6m separating each replicate. Each experimental plot measured 33m by 6.6m, and the total cultivation area was 33m by 29.2m. The seed yams were cultivated during the first planting season in March 2025, properly staked, and weeded regularly to keep the plots free from weeds throughout the experiment. The setup was properly supervised, and every other cultural practice in farm maintenance was duly observed.

Measurements were taken on tuber length (cm), tuber girth/size (cm), number of tubers per planting technique and the tuber fresh weight (t/ha) which began from the point of harvesting in November, 2025. Data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics tool and the Duncan harmonic means for separation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

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The experiment assessed the performance of yam under three planting methods—heap/mound, flat/hole, and sack/bag planting using agronomic indicators. Each treatment had five replicates, ensuring consistency in comparison. Yield performances measured were: Tuber length in centimetre, tuber girth in centimetre, number of yam tubers/planting techniques and tuber fresh weight in tons per hectare and presented as follow:

Table 1: Mean distribution of Yield Performance of White Yam (*Descorea rotundata*) variety to different planting techniques for enhancing production

Variables/ treatments	Heap/Mound	Flat	Bag	SEM
a. Yam tuber length (cm)	37.80 ^a .	34.26 ^b	30.40 ^b	4.17
b. Yam tuber girth (cm)	27.60 ^a	26.00 ^b	23.60 ^b	3.21
c. Number of yam tubers	32.00 ^a	29.00 ^b	27.00 ^b	3.21
d. Yam fresh weight (tons/ha)	113.16 ^a	55.02 ^b	45.46 ^c	7.41

Means with the same superscript are not significantly different (p=0.05)

Table 2: ANOVA results on Yield Performance of White Yam (*Descorea rotundata*) variety to different planting techniques for enhancing production

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
a. Yam Length	Between Groups	136.99	2	68.49	3.80	0.053
	Within Groups	216.15	12	18.01		
	Total	353.14	14			
b. Yam Girth	Between Groups	36.40	2	18.20	2.87	0.096
	Within Groups	76.00	12	6.33		
	Total	112.40	14			
c. Yam Number	Between Groups	48.93	2	24.47	4.53	0.034
	Within Groups	64.80	12	5.40		
	Total	113.73	14			
d. Yam Fresh Weight	Between Groups	13426.79	2	6713.40	10.03	0.003
	Within Groups	8034.33	12	669.53		
	Total	21461.12	14			

Source: Field experiment, 2025

a. Yam Tuber Length

The result on the tuber length of white yam (*Descorea rotundata*) variety across the three planting techniques in Table 1a showed that heap/mound planting produced the longest tubers (M = 37.80cm), followed by flat planting (M = 34.26cm), while bag planting yielded the shortest (M = 30.40cm). The observed variations in mean values of tuber length across treatments suggest that planting

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method strongly influences yam growth and tuber length. These findings align with previous studies that emphasized the role of planting techniques in yam productivity by Okonkwo & Eze (2019).

ANOVA results (Table 2a) on the tuber length of white yam (*Descorea rotundata*) variety across the three planting techniques for enhancing production showed an *f*-cal of 3.80 at probability level less than 0.05%, indicating that differences in the means of tuber lengths of the different planting techniques were statistically significant at the 5% alpha level. Duncan's test grouped treatments into overlapping subsets indicates that longer tubers under heap/mound planting may be attributed to deeper soil profiles, improved aeration, and reduced mechanical resistance to tuber expansion which supported Essien et al. (2021) who reported that tuber performance subscribes to deeper soil profiles and well pulverized soils. Though, statistical significance was achieved, but tuber length alone cannot be considered a critical indicator of superiority.

b. Yam Tuber Girth Performance

The result (Table 1b) on yam girth performance showed that heap/mound planting recorded the largest girth ($M = 27.60\text{cm}$), flat planting produced moderately thick tubers ($M = 26.00\text{cm}$), and bag planting recorded the smallest ($M = 23.80\text{cm}$). The observed differences in mean values of tuber size/girth across treatments imply that planting method strongly influences yam size and profitability. This finding agrees with previous finding that highlighted the part of planting techniques in yam productivity by Ogwulumba et al. (2022).

The ANOVA result (Table 2b) on the same tuber size/girth performance of white yam (*Descorea rotundata*) variety to different planting techniques for enhancing production revealed no significant difference as *f*-calculated was 2.87 at probability level greater than 0.05%, indicating that differences in the means of tuber girths of the different planting techniques were not statistically significant at the 5% level of probability. This result implies that tuber girth appears relatively stable across planting methods and may be more influenced by varietal characteristics and soil fertility than by planting technique alone (Babalola et al., 2023).

c. Number of Yam Tubers per planting method

The result (Table 1c) on the number of tubers per planting method showed that heap/mound planting produced the highest number of yam tubers ($M = 32$), flat planting followed ($M = 29$), and bag planting recorded the least ($M = 27$). The experiential variations in mean values of the number of yam tubers per planting method across treatments implies that planting method strongly influences yam growth and the number of yam tubers per planting method. This finding supports previous studies that emphasized the importance of planting methods in yam production and productivity by Okonkwo & Eze (2019).

ANOVA result (Table 2c) on the same number of tubers produced per planting techniques for enhancing yam production showed a significant difference as *f*-calculated was 4.53, at probability level less than 0.05%, an indication that planting method of yam significantly influences tuber initiation. Heap/mound planting likely provided improved soil conditions, such as better nutrient distribution, enhanced moisture retention, and increased rooting volume that promote tuber formation (Ogwulumba et al., 2022).

d. Yam Fresh Weight (t/ha) Performance (Yield)

The result on yam fresh weight performance (Table 1d) showed that heap/mound planting recorded the highest fresh weight ($M = 113.16\text{ t/ha}$), compared to flat planting ($M = 55.02\text{ t/ha}$) and bag planting ($M = 45.46\text{ t/ha}$). The observed differences in mean values of tuber fresh weight performance across treatments depict that planting technique strongly influences tuber weight size and profitability. This finding aligns with previous studies by Ogwulumba et al. (2022) that highlighted the position of planting techniques in yam productivity.

The ANOVA result on the same yam fresh weight performance (Table 2d) reported a highly significant difference as *f*-calculated was 10.03 at probability level less than 0.05%, Duncan's test showed all three methods as statistically distinct, implying that the superior fresh weight under heap/mound planting highlights its effectiveness in enhancing yam productivity. Increased soil depth, better drainage, and improved nutrient uptake likely facilitated larger and heavier tubers (Olatunji et al., 2024; Chen & Yu, 2024). Bag planting, due to limited soil volume and possible moisture stress, produced the lowest weight

CONCLUSION

The result showed that heap/mound planting technique consistently outperformed flat/hole and bag in tuber length and tuber size/gilt, number of tubers and tuber fresh weight, indicating its superiority for vigorous tuber development. The study therefore concluded that where vigorous and appreciable tuber development is desired heap/mound planting is strongly recommended. Though, the choice of planting method in certain cases may depend on resource availability, land conditions, and management objectives.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study recommended the following:

1. Farmers should adopt all the three methods of yam planting depending on resource availability, land conditions, and management objectives.
2. Where vigorous and appreciable tuber development is desired heap/mound planting strongly recommended.

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